

A numerical study on idealised interphase properties of epoxy resin fibre reinforced composites

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SUMMARY

A numerical study has been performed to investigate local damage in composite materials under transverse loading. The effect of different interphases and thermal residual stresses has been considered. Results indicate a strong dependence on damage onset and its evolution from the interphase properties and the presence of residual stress.

Keywords: Damage; Epoxy resin, Interphase; FEA; Residual Stress.

1. Introduction

In the present work, three-dimensional (3D) finite element analyses have been carried out to study the overall behaviour, damage onset and its evolution of unidirectional composite materials at the micro-scale. Effects of an interphase with a constant thickness and material properties showing “**idealised**” temperature-dependent properties over the curing and cooling process have been extensively investigated.

2. Finite Element Modelling

The constituent materials used in this investigation are glass fibre and epoxy resin, whose properties are given in [1, 2]. The properties of glass fibre are assumed to remain constant and independent of the temperature change. However, for the epoxy resin, thermal transition temperatures such as the glass transition temperature T_g strongly affect mechanical properties. Therefore, the material properties of the resin are defined as a function of temperature. The following conditions have been used:

- Poisson’s ratio is assumed to be temperature independent ($\nu = 0.35$).
- To evaluate the variation of Young’s modulus E over the temperature range from curing to room temperature, the total temperature range has been divided into three regions (Fig.1) [3].

Fig.1 - Mechanical behaviour during the cooling and curing process.

Fig.2 - Unit cell.

The unit cells are a three-dimensional (3D) solid and the fibre volume fraction is $V_f=70\%$. A degradation scheme [2, 4], together with the residual stress analysis was programmed into a user-defined material subroutine (UMAT) interfaced with the commercial finite element code ABAQUS Standard [5]. The behaviour of the matrix and

the fibre was assumed to be linear elastic until damage was predicted. The response after damage occurred was also linear elastic but with degraded moduli. In these FEM studies two loading conditions on have been applied to the unit cell shown in Fig.2, namely:

- 1) transverse loading on the y -direction,
- 2) transverse loading on the z -direction.

Two values of the Young's moduli for the interphase ($E_{\text{interphase}}$) have been considered, namely: 1a) $E_{\text{interphase-soft}}=1.50\text{GPa}$ (softer interphase); 2a) $E_{\text{interphase-stiff}}=7.45\text{GPa}$ (stiffer interphase). Finally, different values of the interphase ultimate strength (Table 1 and Table 2) have been accounted for in these investigations.

3. Finite Element Results

Effect of different interphase material properties and residual stress on transverse (y -direction loading conditions are summarised in Table1 and table-2. Numerical results indicate a strong dependence on damage onset from the interphase properties and the presence of residual stress. In particular analyses have shown that the amount of residuals is very high in the stiff interphase. Therefore, stiff interphases are likely to introduce detrimental effects on the overall mechanical behaviour of unidirectional composite materials at their microscale.

Table 1 – Numerical results for a unit cell with a stiff interphase under transverse loading (y -direction).

STIFF INTERPHASE - $E_{\text{interphase-stiff}}=7.45\text{GPa}$				
$\sigma_{\text{u,INTERPHASE}}$ [MPa]	No Residual Stress	Residual Stress	No Residual Stress	Residual Stress
	RVE Ultimate Strength [MPa]		RVE Failure onset	
20	23.0	Failure during cooling process	INTERPHASE	INTERPHASE
40	23.0		INTERPHASE	INTERPHASE
60	33.0	4.3	INTERPHASE	INTERPHASE
80	43.0	31.5	MATRIX	INTERPHASE
100	43.0	51.0	MATRIX	MATRIX
120	43.0	51.0	MATRIX	MATRIX
140	43.0	51.0	MATRIX	MATRIX

Table 2 – Numerical results for a unit cell with a soft interphase under transverse loading (y -direction).

SOFT INTERPHASE - $E_{\text{interphase-soft}}=1.50\text{GPa}$				
$\sigma_{\text{u,INTERPHASE}}$ [MPa]	No Residual Stress	Residual Stress	No Residual Stress	Residual Stress
	RVE Ultimate Strength [MPa]		RVE Failure onset	
20	11.8	7.8	INTERPHASE	INTERPHASE
40	23.0	29.0	INTERPHASE	INTERPHASE
60	34.0	41.0	INTERPHASE	INTERPHASE
80	45.0	51.5	MATRIX	MATRIX/INTERPHASE
100	45.0	51.5	MATRIX	MATRIX
120	45.0	51.5	MATRIX	MATRIX

References

- [1] M.J. Hinton, P D Soden, A S Kaddour, "Failure Criteria in Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composites - The World-Wide Failure Exercise", Elsevier Science Publishers (2004).
- [2] A. R. Maligno, A.C. Long, N.A. Warrior "Finite element investigations on the microstructure of unidirectional composite materials", eXpress Polymer Letters 2008, 2(9), 665-676.
- [3] Zhang, Y., Xia, Z., Ellyin, F., "Evolution and influence of residual stress/strains of fiber reinforced laminates" Composites Science and Technology 64 (2004), pp. 1613-1621.
- [4] D. Blacketter, D. E. Walrath, and A. C. Hansen, "Modelling Damage in a Plain Weave Fabric Reinforced Composite Materials", Journal of Composites Technology and Research 15 (1993), pp. 136-142.
- [5] ABAQUS/Standard User's Manual, Version 6.5, Vol.3.